

Canada Research Chair in Media, Disabilities and (Self) Representations

Questionnaire Media production

Linked to the Disability and Deafhood Database
chairemediashandicaps.uqam.ca/database/

PURPOSE OF THE CRCMHA

IDENTIFY groups living with one or more disabilities that are predominantly represented in the Canadian media (1980-2020) as well as the characteristics of these (self)representations, the characters represented and their authors;

To better UNDERSTAND the relation between contemporary media representations of disability (2000-2020) and their uses by people with disabilities;

Determine measures likely to IMPROVE over time the presence and inclusion of people with disabilities in media content through the development and implementation of inclusive "media policies" promoting the full social participation of the groups concerned.

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UQÀM | **Chaire de recherche du Canada
sur les médias, les handicaps
et les (auto)représentations**
FACULTÉ DE COMMUNICATION
Université du Québec à Montréal

/bin
Bureau des
initiatives
numériques

Chaires de recherche
du Canada

Canada Research
Chairs

Canada

1) Title of production (French)

Open data

2) Title of production (English)

Open data

3) Title of production (details)

Closed data / Multiple choice

1
(...)
50

4) Produced by

Open data

5) Production type

Closed data / Multiple choice

Comic strip
Film (short and medium-length)
Film (feature)
Virtual reality
Graphic novel
Television series
Webseries
Other

6) Production category

Closed data / Multiple choice

Documentary
Docufiction
Fiction
Other

7) Main genre of the production

Closed data / Multiple choice

Action / Adventure
Art / Art film
Biographical
Comedy / Drama
Comedy / Humorous
Crime
Drama
Erotic
Essay
Experimental
Fantastic / Fantasy
Historical
Horror

Musical
Romantic / Sentimental
Romantic comedy
Science Fiction
Thriller / Mystery
Western
Youth

8) Main theme of the production

Closed data / Multiple choice

Death / Bereavement
Disability
Family
Initiation story
Love / Friendship
Marginality
Nature
Politics
Professional environment
Sexuality
Spirituality
Sports
Revenge
Travel
War

9) Year

1980
(...)
2040

10) Duration

Open data

11) Duration details

Open data

12) Original language

Closed data / Multiple choice

English
French
Multilingual
Other

13) Production contains one or more passages in sign language

Check box

14) Country – Provinces/Territories

Closed data / Multiple choice

Canada
Canada-Alberta
Canada-British Columbia
Canada-Manitoba
Canada-New Brunswick
Canada-Newfoundland and Labrador
Canada-Northwest Territories
Canada-Nova Scotia
Canada-Nunavut
Canada-Ontario
Canada-Prince Edward Island
Canada-Quebec
Canada-Saskatchewan
Canada-Yukon
Canadian co-production
International co-production

15) Awards

Closed data / Multiple choice

None
Minor award
Prestigious award

16) Awards (details) (French)

Open data

16B) Awards (details) (English)

Open data

17) Production adapted from a real-life event

Check box

18) Production adapted from another work

Open data

19) Adaptations have been produced based on this work

Open data

20) Official summary (French)

Open data

21) Official summary (English)

Open data

22) Diegetic era is the same as production era

Closed data / Multiple choice

No
Yes
Timeless / Anhistorical story
Unknown

23) Diegetic era is the same as production era (details)

Open data

24) Notes on production

Open data

25) Problems with production

Open data

26) Status of analysis

Closed data / Multiple choice

Complete
Partial
Production not found
In process

27) Status of analysis (details) (French)

Open data

27B) Status of analysis (details) (English)

Case ouverte